

Joule Heating study in scaled Cu, Co and Ru interconnects

Melina Lofrano, Olalla Varela Pedreira, Kristof Croes and Zsolt Tókei

imec
Leuven, Belgium
Melina.Lofrano@imec.be

Abstract - We discuss Joule heating effects in scaled interconnects, where Ru and Co lines have been compared with standard Cu interconnects. Due to the combination of a high electrical resistivity of the metal and a poor thermal conductivity of the IMD, the Joule heating in these lines is significantly higher compared to Cu lines. Using a finite element model that is calibrated at wider dimensions (22nm lines width), we predict that Joule heating in 10nm wide lines can become significant at use conditions. We also shown that the IMD plays an important role on the Joule heating effect, where we show that integrating metal lines in an IMD with a higher thermal conductivity leads to a significantly reduced Joule heating and consequently its effect on the neighboring lines can be limited as well.

Keywords—BEOL, Scaled interconnect, Joule heating, Finite element model, Co lines, Ru lines

I. INTRODUCTION

The miniaturization of microelectronic component leads to an aggressively scaling of interconnect dimensions. One of the challenges of downscaling Cu is an increase in via/line resistance.

Alternative metals, like Co and Ru, are considered as possible candidates to replace Cu. One of the reasons is their potential to be integrated in sub 10nm wide lines with high reliability [1-4]. Concerning reliability, lines with Co or Ru show excellent electromigration behavior [2,3,5,6]. With respect to dielectric breakdown, Ru lines shown the potential to be barrierless [5,6], where only a thin adhesion layer is required.

One reliability aspect that still needs to be investigated is Joule heating. The increase of required current density and electrical resistivity due to scaling, combined with the low thermal conductivity of low-k dielectric materials, results in an increased concern of Joule heating at operating conditions. These higher temperatures can trigger several reliability issues, such as an increase in mechanical stresses which could lead to delamination and enhanced electromigration.

In this paper we investigate the Joule heating generated in scaled Co, Ru and Cu lines. Finite element modeling (FEM) has been used to extend the learning obtained by Joule heating measurements on wider dimensions to scaled technology nodes. Joule heating in 10nm wide lines and its effect on the adjacent lines are predicted.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

For the experimental part, we used interconnects integrated in 44nm metal pitch using 300mm Si wafers. Measurements were conducted on single damascene lines with a CD of 22nm and a length of 100 μ m. To test smaller areas, a backfill approach with SiO₂ was used to obtain lines with nominal CD of 10nm [4]. To quantify the heating, currents are sent through the lines and the average heating is estimated based on the R. vs. T and R vs. I trends through (1):

$$\Delta T = \frac{R}{R_0} \frac{1}{TCR} = BI^2 \quad (1)$$

Through TCR measurements, the effective cross-sectional area can also be calculated and this allows to do benchmarking of different metal/dielectric structures with metal areas ranging from 100 to 1250nm².

In [4] we show typical curves ΔT vs. I where we immediately see that metallization with Ru, either as liner or as full metallization, heats up more than the Cu systems.

Fig. 1. ΔT versus I curves for Cu and Ru metallization

The Joule heating slope, B (1), can be used for benchmarking of the different systems as a function of cross-sectional area. This benchmark is shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Joule heating slope for different materials as a function of cross sectional area

The results show that Cu lines present the lowest Joule heating slope, while Co and Ru are more prone to Joule heating. It is also observed that Joule heating becomes more severe towards smaller line dimensions. It is important to notice that the downscaling increases the electrical resistivity of the metals due to electron scattering [7]. The electrical resistivity calculated based on measured resistance for lines around 1000nm² showed a resistivity of $\sim 50\text{n}\Omega\text{m}$ for Cu lines, while Co and Ru present a much higher values, ~ 137 and $\sim 140\text{n}\Omega\text{m}$ respectively. For areas smaller than 250nm² the resistivity of these materials increases significantly: $\sim 80\text{n}\Omega\text{m}$ for Cu, $\sim 170\text{n}\Omega\text{m}$ and $\sim 220\text{n}\Omega\text{m}$ for Co and Ru.

III. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A 3D FEM has been used to understand the Joule heating observed in the electrical measurements discussed in session II. The model has been built up corresponding to the test structure considering 22nm wide and 50nm deep lines. Figure 3 shows the detail of FEM. There have been 3 variants: a) standard Cu lines with a TaN barrier integrated in low-k b) Co lines with a TiN barrier integrated in low-k and c) Ru lines with a thin adhesion layer integrated in low-k.

Fig. 3. Finite Element Model details

In the model, the temperature at the bottom of the Si has been kept constant. Through the middle line, the so-called active line, a current density was applied. The material properties used in the analysis are described in the Table 1. The electrical resistivity of the metal lines has been characterized internally while for the thermal conductivity, bulk material properties were assumed.

TABLE I. MATERIAL PROPERTIES USED IN FEM

	Co	Cu	Ru
Thermal conductivity [W/ (m · K)]	100	400	120
Electrical resistivity at 20°C (nΩm)	137	50	140
Specific Heat [J / (kg · K)]	420	390	240
Mass density [g/cm ³]	8.86	8.96	12.37

The coupled electric-thermal analysis has been performed using a commercial FEM software, MSC Marc[®]. The simulated temperature increase of the active line due to Joule heating has been compared with the measurement results. Figure 4 shows the comparison between measurement and simulation results for Cu, Co and Ru lines. A very good agreement with measurement results is found for all line materials considered in this work. The results show that Cu lines presents the lowest Joule heating. At 1mA, which corresponds to $\sim 90\text{MA}/\text{cm}^2$, the Cu line heats up to $\sim 35^\circ\text{C}$. The Co and Ru lines show much higher Joule heating. At 1mA, the temperature rises up to $\sim 152^\circ\text{C}$ for Co and $\sim 177^\circ\text{C}$ for Ru.

Fig. 4. Temperature rise due to Joule heating for 22nm wide Cu, Co and Ru lines. Simulation and measurement results

IV. PREDICTIVE MODELLING

Now the FEM are calibrated, we can use it to explore the Joule heating effect in advanced technology nodes. For this purpose, Co and Ru lines were modeled as being 10nm wide, 20nm deep and 100μm long. The electrical resistivity for these lines dimension was characterized internally and discussed in session I. Figure 5 shows the estimated Joule heating effect for 10nm wide Co and Ru lines integrated in different IMDs.

Fig. 5. Temperature rise due to Joule heating as a function of current for 10nm wide a) Ru and b) Co lines

Figure 5 shows that Ru has a higher Joule heating than Co, due to its higher electrical resistivity. Joule heating is caused by a combination of high resistivity of the metal lines and the low thermal conductivity of the IMD. This low thermal conductivity inhibits the heat to flow away. Figure 5 shows that the Joule heating for lines integrated in airgap and low-k are higher compared to lines integrated in SiO₂. The fact that Ru/airgap and R/low-k are similar could sound counter intuitive since air presents a lower thermal conductivity (~0.001W/m°C) compared to low-k (~0.1W/m°C). However, as these lines are in direct contact with the cap layer which in this case is the main heating path as it presents a higher thermal conductivity (~1.3W/m°C). Figure 6 shows that the heat is conducted away mainly through the cap making the temperature increase very similar for both low-k and airgap. In the case of SiO₂ the heat spreading all around the lines what decreases the temperature in the metal lines.

Fig. 6. Heat spreading in case: a) low-k, b) airgap and c) SiO₂

Table II shows the temperature increase for our cases at 100μA. When using low-k or airgaps, >10°C temperature increase is expected in single line for these currents in these dimensions, where of an IMD with a lower thermal conductivity, like SiO₂, the predicted temperature increase is significantly lower.

TABLE II. TEMPERATURE RISE DUE JOULE HEATING FOR 100μA OF CURRENT

	Low-k	Airgap	SiO ₂
Ru	15	15	3
Co	11	--	2

The effect of self-heating on the neighboring lines has also been investigated. Figure 7 shows the temperature in the adjacent lines for a maximum current of 100μA.

Fig. 7. Temperature increase in the neighboring lines for a) Ru and b) Co lines at 100μA.

The lateral heat spreading in a 10nm line/space shows a high thermal gradient across the IMD. The IMD acts as a thermal isolation layer, inhibiting the heat to flow and causing self-heating on the adjacent lines. It can be seen that lines integrated in low-k and airgap present high self-heating on the neighboring lines, which will have a negative impact on electromigration and which will increase the risk of delamination at the interface between the IMD and the lines due to the thermal stress. A way to mitigate this effect is the use of high thermal conductivity IMDs. Figure 7 shows that lines integrated in SiO₂ (~1.5W/m°C) are not expected to be affected by self-heating.

V. CONCLUSION

We presented a Joule heating study in scaled Cu, Co and Ru interconnects, where we used a calibrated FEM model to extrapolate Joule heating measurements on wider dimensions to scaled line widths. Due to the combination of a high electrical resistivity of the metal lines and a poor thermal conductivity of the IMD, we predict high Joule heating in the scaled interconnect lines at use conditions, where Co and Ru showed a higher Joule heating compared to standard Cu lines. Lines with a CD of 10nm show to be susceptible to Joule heating at relatively lower currents, which suggests a reliability risk. IMDs with a higher thermal conductivity can help to decrease the Joule heating on small lines. At 100μA, temperature rises in Ru lines decreased from 15°C in low-k to 3°C in SiO₂.

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